

A GENERAL UNDERSTANDING OF THE ROMANCE-GERMANIC LANGUAGES

*Sh. Safarova*¹

Abstract:

In this article, you will get a general understanding of the language, origin and development of the language. In addition, you will learn from this article about the definition of language as a system of systems, the assumptions made about the Romance-Germanic languages and related languages.

Key words: Language, the development of language, language units, language systems, language families, Romance languages, Germanic languages.

Language is the most important tool of communication between people, it is formed in the process of development of society and serves universal interests. Since the emergence and development of language is related to the development of society, the source of learning of all sciences that think about human development is related to language. The nature of language, its essence, its function in human society, its structure and the interaction of the elements that make up this structure, its internal mechanism, principles of operation require scientific study and comprehensive research of language. Language is a product of human society. Without language, it is impossible to know and study any reality and phenomenon, the place of human in nature and society, the ways of society's development (5:3p).

The question of the emergence of language – when and where language appeared, how many languages were there at first, what these or those languages were like and the perfect scientific answer to such questions has not yet been found. There are only scientific assumptions in this regard. According to some scientists, the language appeared about five hundred years ago (3:10p).

Nations develop and become nations in certain historical conditions of society. For the emergence and development of a nation, it is necessary to have an economic relationship between a large number of people. The main characteristics of a nation are: common territory, common language, common culture and spiritual unity. The association of people who embody these characteristics can be called a nation. We call the language of such an association the national language. Linguistic unity and its free development is one of the main characteristics of the nation. The national language will have its own literary form. This form of the national language is common to every dialect of this nation. The cultural heritage of every nation is reflected in this language. Each language goes through a different period of development. It cannot be said that any language has been developing by itself since its inception. It is known that language is related to people. Language does not develop by itself, it develops and changes only because society uses language. So, the history of language development is inextricably linked with the history of society [3:15p].

Definition of language as a system of systems was carried out by many scientists. In particular, the Uzbek scientist A. Sobirov specifically researched this issue in his doctoral dissertation. In this doctoral work, the idea is put forward that elements are the objects that make up the system in general, and the element is an indivisible unit that keeps its own characteristics in the system. But indivisibility is a relative concept. An element itself consists of a system, which in turn consists of elements. In other words, the element does not exist outside the system in its entirety. But it is necessary to distinguish elements from separate parts of the system. The function of a part of a system can be formed by any group of elements that are involuntarily and naturally separated. In other words, subsystems (small systems) are created within the system [1:53p].

The structure, grammatical features of some languages, the origin of words in these languages, word forms and meanings are very close to each other. Such languages are derived from a common root language and are called sister languages. A group of languages that are close to each other in terms of grammatical structure and other features is called a language family [5:44p].

Currently, the group of Germanic languages includes the following languages:

a) English language. The number of speakers of this language has reached four hundred million. Speakers of this language live in Great Britain, Ireland, North America, Canada, South American Union and other places. English is the official language of several countries, such as Great Britain (the capital is London), the United States of America (the capital is Washington), Canada (Ottawa);

¹ *Shodiya Safarova, Student of Sam SIFL*

- b) German language. German is the official language of Berlin which is the capital of the Federal Republic of Germany, and Vienna which is the capital of the Republic of Austria. The number of speakers of this language exceeds one hundred million;
- c) Danish language. This language is the official language of Copenhagen, the capital of Denmark, and the number of speakers of this language is about four (4) million;
- d) Swedish language. It is the official language of Stockholm, the capital of Sweden, and is spoken by more than seven (7) million people; d)
- e) Norwegian language. This language is the official language of Oslo, the capital of Norway, and it is spoken by three (3,5) and a half million people;
- f) Dutch language. This language is the official language of Amsterdam, the capital of the Netherlands, and is spoken by thirteen (13) million people; j)
- g) Icelandic language. It is the official language of Reykjavik, the capital of Iceland, and it is spoken by two hundred and fifty thousand (250) people; Among the dead languages, the Visigothic and Ostrogothic languages also belong to the group of Germanic languages.
- The following languages belong to the Romance language group:
- a) French. This language is the official language of French.
- b) Italian. This language is the official language of Italy.
- c) Spanish. This language is the official language of Spain.
- d) Portuguese. This language is official language of Portugal.
- e) Romanian. This language is the official language of the Republic of Romania.
- f) Moldovan. This language is the official language of the Republic of
- g) Sardinian. This language is spoken by more than one million people who live on the island of Sardinia, which belongs to Italy.
- h) Catalan. This language is spoken by over five million people, mainly in Spain.
- i) Rhaeto-Romance. This language is spoken by 550,000 people, most of whom live in Italy [5:18].
- Ancient languages such as Latin, Oscan, and Umbrian are also part of the Romance language group.

References:

- [1]. Abulkasimovna, E. Z. (2021). *Comparing Uzbek proverbs and English proverbs in literary. Thematics Journal of Social Sciences*, 7(1).
- [2]. Abulkasimovna, E. Z. (2022). *Synonymous analysis of professional words in English and Uzbek. Frontline Social Sciences and History Journal*, 2(05), 15-22.
- [3]. Asadova, C., Ulug'bekova, S., & Shamsiyeva, K. (2024, April). *Ingiliz tilida lug'at yodlashning samarali usullari. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 152-155).*
- [4]. Ashirboyev Samixon "O'zbek dialektologiyasi" Toshkent-2016.
- [5]. Bosim To'ychiboyev, Bo'riboy Hasanov "O'zbek dialektologiyasi" Toshkent-2004
- [6]. Makhmudova, J., & Asadova, C. (2024, April). *The goals and objectives of using game activities in education. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 194-197).*
- [7]. Nazar Rajabov "O'zbek shevashunosligi" Toshkent- 1996 30-bet
- [8]. T. J. Enazarov, V.A.Karimjonova "O'zbek dialektologiyasi" Toshkent-2012 23-bet
- [9]. Yoqub Saidov "O'zbek dialektologiyasi" Buxoro-2021 4-5-betlar
- [10]. Salimovna, A. C. (2023). *Teaching children how to set adequate goals and strategies. finland" modern scientific research: topical issues, achievements and innovations"*, 14(1).
- [11]. Обруева Г.Х. О сдвиге имени собственного в разряд нарицательных слов во фразеологии английского языка. *Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (22), 2010. – С.100-102.
- [12]. Асадова, Ч. (2019). *Абстрактные существительные в английском и русском языках. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (1-3), 82-84.
- [13]. Асадова, Ч. (2022). *Xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda yosh davriga xos xususiyatlar. Анализ актуальных проблем, инноваций, традиций, решений и художественной литературы в преподавании иностранных языков*, 1(01), 225-226.